

CONSCIOUSNESS AND SUBCONSCIOUS ACTIVITY AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract: This article explains in detail what the subconscious is, how to use it, as well as how to apply it to our lives and the miraculous changes that occur after that. The concept of the subconscious is very important. It is also complicated and many researches have been conducted in the science of psychology, in this sense, the Canadian scientist John Kehoe in one of his most famous books "Subconscious is capable of everything" taught how to use the subconscious in life and this the article will focus on this work.

Key words: subconscious, John Kehoe, positive and negative thoughts, hardware, Alexander Graham Bell, holographic universe, quantum physics, David Bohm.

The second definition of consciousness is that it expresses a clear distinction between the subject and the object, that is, a person determines what belongs to the concept of "I". The first person in the history of the world of living organisms, who separated himself from it and contrasted himself with his environment, keeps this conflict and difference in his mind. Among living beings, he is the only one capable of self-knowledge, that is, of directing his mental activity to self-research. A person consciously evaluates his actions and himself in general. Separation of "I" from "not me" is a process that everyone experiences in childhood, and it happens in the process of self-realization. The third definition of consciousness is to ensure the purposeful activity of a person. The creation of activity goals is part of the function of the mind. In this, the motivations of the activity arise and are estimated. Voluntary decisions are made. How the actions are performed is taken into account. Appropriate corrections will be made to it and so on.

Consciousness is the highest form of mental activity. It is only a human phenomenon. Consciousness, its essence is the most important question. one of the problems. At first, they tried to explain consciousness within the framework

of religious and mythological views. The linear explanation of consciousness is based on interpreting it as a divine phenomenon, a miracle created by God. In many religions, human consciousness is described as a manifestation of the great divine intelligence. The roots of such views are very old. However, they still have many supporters. He who admits that the universe and man are created, considers that Consciousness is also the power of creation. Unconscious (in psychology) - mental processes and states that occur without the participation of consciousness. Consciousness is often invisible in body movement, memory, imagination. It occurs in response effects caused by real but imperceptible stimuli, in actions that are originally conscious and become automatic as a result of repetition, and in other situations. Mac, a man returns home lost in his thoughts, and in any case comes without straying from the path.

If he perceives a danger, he will take a protective action even before he understands the cause and nature of this danger. Pathological phenomena such as delusions, hallucinations, sleep, during hypnosis, lunaticism and sleeplessness that occur in the patient's psyche. mental activity that occurs during Freud interprets consciousness in a purely irrationalist way. According to him, there is an irreconcilable opposition between consciousness and Consciousness. All human behavior is determined by this contradiction. Mind cannot be understood and noticed by man, it is the abode of eternal desires in man. To the field of unconsciousness: biological needs (sexual inclinations, natural needs, need for food, etc.); suppressing wishes (a vain attempt to win someone's love, unfulfilled dreams, secret resentment); psychic phenomena occurring in a dream (dreaming); response reactions to imperceptible, but real effects ("subsensory" effects); actions that were previously understood, but became automatic due to repetitions and therefore became incomprehensible; includes certain inclinations and others in relation to activities whose purpose is not understood. Unconscious events include some pathological events such as delusions and hallucinations that occur in the psyche of a sick person.

We will discuss with you the difference between the concepts of consciousness and subconsciousness in psychology. Consciousness is a tool that can receive and analyze all information from the external environment during our life. That is, it is the apparatus that manages and controls what we think, what we do, what we are surprised by. And I call the subconscious "Big golden box", because it stores all the information, for example: you were once bitten by a puppy, but you You don't remember when and what time that event happened, what clothes you were wearing that day, but every time you see a puppy, you begin to fear

inside without knowing it, because this event is stored in your subconscious. . Not only events, but also positive and negative thoughts, dreams, worries, fears, and blocks remain in our consciousness. The subconscious mind is so powerful that if we learn to use it properly, we can miraculously change our lives for the better. Our mind stores ten percent of information, that is, what it needs, and the rest is stored in our subconscious, that is, our subconscious controls us. For example: a person who smokes cigarettes knows that they are harmful, but continues to smoke them, that is, even though he knows that he is doing something wrong, he cannot give up because he is addicted to it in his mind. Therefore, if we form our consciousness correctly, we can achieve success in all areas. The English writer Shakespeare has wonderful words: My friend Horatio, there are many things in the bright world that our wise men have not even dreamed of⁸. It is not necessary to know the laws of physics to use the power of the mind, after all, it is not necessary to learn how it is structured to control the telephone. Few people know the internal structure of the phone, but this does not prevent people from using the phone. Our subconscious is such a great power that only a few people know how to use it properly. "I can't tell you how powerful he is. I only know that it exists" ⁹, said Alexander Graham Bell, the inventor of the telephone. Every created invention is created with love and affection, for example, if it were not for the love of the Ryde brothers for aviation, we would not be flying in airplanes now. Humans are perfect is a biological mechanism, but not everyone uses the opportunities given to it by nature. Intuition, inner voice, subconscious ... these words have different sounds, but they are united by a common meaning. The ability to anticipate events, make the right decisions, listen to the signals of your body or the world around you, acquire knowledge that helps in everyday life - all this is available to everyone from birth.

References:

1. Abdullaeva, M., Nikitina, M., & Sharipova, S. (2023). Oily types of nervous activity and temperaments. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(2), 47-50.
2. Abdullaeva, M., Ruzmetova, F., Madrakhimova, A., & Kazokova, M. (2022). The importance of the oral method in forming imaginations about nature in children. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(12), 310-312.
3. Abdullaeva, M. (2022). Fauna and ecology of butterflies of the family notodontidae of the lower amudarya state biosphere reserve. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(12), 264-267.

4. Abdullayeva, M., qizi Yangibayeva, N. S., & Muxtarova, I. R. (2023). Memory and its laws. Science and Education, 4(2), 93-95.
5. Abdullayeva, M., & Ismailova, A. (2023, January). Preserving mother nature is our sacred duty. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 106-108).
6. Abdullayeva, M. R., & Ismailova, A. (2023). Health and a healthy lifestyle. Science and Education, 4(2), 201-203.
7. Abdullayeva, M. R., & Sharibova, I. (2023). Organizing practical work in passing natural sciences in primary grades. Science and Education, 4(2), 1048-1054.
8. Yangibayeva, N. (2023). THE MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF ANIMAL LIFE. Евразийский журнал технологий и инноваций, 1(9), 88-90.
9. Abdullayeva, M., qizi Yangibayeva, N. S., & Muxtarova, I. R. (2023). Memory and its laws. Science and Education, 4(2), 93-95.
10. Yangibayeva, N., & Pirova, F. (2022). OBSERVATION IS THE LEADING METHOD OF NATURE LEARNING IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 2(11), 47-49.
11. Yangibayeva, N., & Yusupova, M. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF PERCEPTION AND THINKING IN PSYCHOLOGY. ITS PRINCIPLES. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 2(11), 50-53.
12. Qizi, Y. N. S., Saboxon, O., Risolat, A., & Salomat, S. (2022). ORAL TEACHING METHODS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL NATURE CLASSES. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 2(11), 88-90.
13. Shernafasova, H., & Yangibayeva, N. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS. Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика, 1(19), 31-34.
14. Egamberdiyeva, M., qizi Yangibayeva, N. S., qizi Abdusharipova, M. X., & Bekchanov, X. O. R. (2022). Ertaklardan maktabgacha va boshlang'ich maktab yoshidagi bolalarni axloqiy tarbiyalash vositasi sifatida foydalanish. Science and Education, 3(5), 829-831.
15. Yangibayeva, N. S. Q., Komiljonova, Z., & Ruzibayeva, N. (2022). Natural resources and human influence on natural resources. To give elementary school students the concepts of using natural resources. Science and Education, 3(12), 160-162.

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16. Yusupova, F. H. Q., Yangibayeva, N. S. Q., & Abdusharipova, M. X. Q. (2022). Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ekologik tarbiya maqsadi. Science and Education, 3(5), 661-665.

